

ANALYSIS OF THE ECOLOGICAL STATUS OF CHEMICALLY CONTAMINATED SOILS AND SOIL MORPHOLOGICAL INDICATOR PARAMETERS

O.N. Imomov¹, Z.A. Jabbarov², M.F. Fakhrutdinova³, U.M. Nomozov⁴
National university of Uzbekistan named after Mirzo Ulugbek, Tashkent^{1,2,3,4}
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15225219>

Abstract. *This article examines the degree of chemical contamination, main sources, and consequences of irrigated takyr-meadow and meadow-alluvial soils in the industrialized regions of the Navoi region. During the research, international and modern laboratory methods were applied, and the quality and fertility of the soils were assessed based on their physical, chemical, and biological indicator parameters. The research results have significant scientific and practical importance in developing recommendations for improving the condition and increasing the fertility of chemically contaminated areas.*

Keywords: *soil, indicator, physical, chemical, biological, heavy metal.*

Introduction. Currently, irrigated lands account for 9.6% of the total land fund in our Republic, and the main agricultural crops are grown on these irrigated lands. However, the fertility of these soils is not at a normal level. Compared to other environments, soil cover has a greater potential for chemical contamination. Specifically, gases released into the atmosphere or chemicals entering water sources eventually settle into the soil cover over time, leading to soil contamination [14]. The spread of chemical contamination over large areas is largely influenced by industrial activities and related processes, which have resulted in several negative consequences for soil cover [15]. The impact of contamination is classified as strong or weak. Activities such as mining can cause severe and rapid effects on the soil, damaging its upper layers, whereas other pollutants may affect the soil more slowly and weakly over time [16].

Among different types of contamination, chemical pollution is considered the most harmful because it significantly affects the physical, chemical, and biological properties of the soil. Most importantly, it negatively impacts biological diversity [10]. When soil conditions change, biochemical and oxidation-reduction reactions within the soil are also altered, leading to a sharp decline in soil fertility. This, in turn, affects soil health, quality, and fertility indicators [2]. The degree of soil contamination is assessed based on changes in the amount of humus, the total and mobile forms of nutrients, and the concentration of pollutants exceeding or decreasing below the permissible PEC limits [3]. Understanding soil health, quality, and fertility indicators is one of the best methods for the targeted use of soil. Identifying and managing soil indicator parameters allows for better control over soil health, fertility, and quality improvement [4, 13].

METHODOLOGY. Indicators for assessing soil health, quality, and fertility are based on the overall properties of the soil. These indicators help evaluate soil conditions through analytical studies [6]. This includes studying the soil's physical, chemical, and biological indicators, assessing its health characteristics, and determining fertility levels. Soil indicators are generally categorized into physical, chemical, and biological indicator groups [5]. Assessing soil property indicators through indicators aimed at eliminating soil chemical contamination is also important

for evaluating soil fertility and economic profitability [21]. The increase in soil contamination due to chemical pollutants, the reduction of organic matter, and the intensified impact of pollutants lead to changes in stress-related indicators in soil-plant interactions and soil itself. This negatively affects soil enzyme activity, reduces soil biodiversity, and decreases the diversity of beneficial organisms, ultimately leading to a decline in soil health [6]. On an international scale, the primary 39 indicators used to assess soil health, quality, and fertility provide essential information about the condition of the soil. These indicators serve as measurable parameters or characteristics reflecting soil status [5]. Chemical contamination of the soil, the concentration of heavy metals, and the exceeding of permissible PEC limits contribute to the process of soil chemical pollution.

Table 1

Potential indicators for assessing soil health, quality, and fertility

[Moebius-Klun, B.N., Thies, J.E. va Abawi, G.S. 2009.] [14].

Physical indicators	Biological indicators	Chemical indicators
Bulk density	Root health assessment	Phosphorus
Macro-porosity	Beneficial nematode population	Nitrate
Meso-porosity	Parasitic nematode population	Potassium
Micro-porosity	Potentially mineralizable nitrogen	pH
Field capacity	Decomposition rate	Magnesium
Soil granulation at 10 kPa	Organic particles	Calcium
Penetration resistance	Active carbon	Iron
Saturated hydraulic conductivity	Weed seed bank	Aluminum
Dry aggregate size (<0.25 mm)	Microbial respiration rate	Manganese
Dry aggregate size (0.25 - 2 mm)	Glomalin (glycoprotein)	Zinc
Dry aggregate size (2 - 8 mm)	Organic matter composition	Copper
Wet aggregate stability (0.25 - 2 mm)		Exchangeable acidity
Wet aggregate stability (2 - 8 mm)		
Surface hardness (measured by penetrometer)		
Subsurface hardness (measured by penetrometer)		
Field infiltration rate		

These indicators are scientifically proven to be used for assessing soil quality and fertility, as well as its ability to support plant growth and nutrient cycling. Preventive measures against soil chemical contamination caused by the chemical industry help clarify the factors contributing to pollution and provide a scientific basis for certain assessment methods developed to evaluate soil contamination [18].

In assessing soil chemical contamination, evaluation tools and soil quality parameters can be analyzed using unified indicators.

Research area. The industrial enterprises located in the research area, particularly the long-term operations of "Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combinat" JSC, have led to changes in soil indicators. As a result, soil contamination with pollutants has been observed, including chemical contamination caused by various compounds and oxides of Zn, Cu, Ni, Cd, Pb, Hg, Cr, As, Ba, Co, La, Lu, Ag, Cr, and Cs [19]. It has been established that the chemical contamination

of irrigated soils in the research area has affected soil health, quality, and fertility. The primary sources of contamination include the "Cement Production" Joint-Stock Company, Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Plant, Navoi Azot Joint-Stock Company, and the Hydorradioelectroenergy Station (HRES) located in Karmana district, Navoi region. The dispersion of chemical pollutants from these sources into the environment is significantly influenced by wind factors. (**Figure 1.**)

Figure 1. Geographical Location of the Research Area

These industrial enterprises release pollutants mainly in the form of gases, dust, and aerosols into the atmosphere, where they disperse. This leads to changes in the physical, chemical, and biological indicator properties of irrigated soils surrounding the industrial area, affecting soil health, quality, and fertility. Additionally, it contributes to the alteration of air composition in the environment, exceeding the PEC threshold and causing further changes [12]. Soil profiles were excavated, and samples were collected from the research area along the predominant wind direction. Specifically, samples were taken from the northwestern direction around the industrial zone of Navoi region, including the "Navoi Khizilkum Cement" JSC and the "Cement Production" Joint-Stock Company. The geographical coordinates of the research area can be found in the following table.

Table 2

Geographical coordinates of the studied areas

Navoi Cement Plant	
Northern point	N 40°05'04" Northern latitude, E 65°17'15" Eastern longitude
Southern point	N 40°05'03" Northern latitude, E 65°17'13" Eastern longitude
Eastern point	N 40°09'04" Northern latitude, E 65°17'10" Eastern longitude
Western point	N 40°13'07" Northern latitude, E 65°18'08" Eastern longitude
Navoi NMMC (Navoi Mining & Metallurgical Combine)	
Northern point	N 40°05'45" Northern latitude, E 65°21'05" Eastern longitude
Southern point	N 40°05'50" Northern latitude, E 65°20'45" Eastern longitude

Eastern point	N 40°05'50" Northern latitude, E 65°20'35" Eastern longitude
Western point	N 40°06'50" Northern latitude, E 65°21'15" Eastern longitude
Navoi Azot JSC	
Northern point	N 40°07'15" Northern latitude, E 65°19'15" Eastern longitude
Southern point	N 40°07'30" Northern latitude, E 65°19'30" Eastern longitude
Eastern point	N 40°07'45" Northern latitude, E 65°19'45" Eastern longitude
Western point	N 40°09'15" Northern latitude, E 65°18'30" Eastern longitude
Navoi HRES	
Northern point	N 40°07'15" Northern latitude, E 65°19'15" Eastern longitude
Southern point	N 40°07'30" Northern latitude, E 65°19'30" Eastern longitude
Eastern point	N 40°07'45" Northern latitude, E 65°19'45" Eastern longitude
Western point	N 40°09'15" Northern latitude, E 65°18'30" Eastern longitude
Background (FON)	
Northern point	N 40°01'45" Northern latitude, E 65°35'22" Eastern longitude
Southern point	N 40°01'45" Northern latitude, E 65°35'22" Eastern longitude
Eastern point	N 40°01'45" Northern latitude, E 65°35'22" Eastern longitude
Western point	N 40°01'45" Northern latitude, E 65°35'22" Eastern longitude

Figure 2. Wind direction vector in the industrial area

In the research area, there is no involvement of groundwater and surface water in environmental pollution, particularly in the chemical contamination of the soil cover. As of today, as mentioned above, excessive chemical pollutants have entered the soil through air deposition rather than from PEC.

Soil samples were collected along the wind direction from the surroundings of the Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine, Navoi Azot Joint-Stock Company, and the Hydorradioelectroenergy Station (HRES) located in the Karmana district of Navoi region. Soil profile excavation points around Qizilqum Cement.

The contamination of soils around the cement plant mainly occurs due to the release of cement dust. In addition, the soils are also polluted by various emissions carried through atmospheric gas and dust. The dispersion of dust and pollutants is not uniform in all directions around HRES; it is predominantly directed towards the east and northeast. Atmospheric transport mainly affects the northeastern area, leading to higher levels of contamination. Therefore, soil sampling pits were excavated according to the wind direction, and soil samples were collected. In 2023, wind direction observations showed that in 2022, the predominant wind came from the east, accounting for 24% of the total.

Additionally, winds from the southeast made up 19%, from the west 6%, from the southwest 11%, from the northwest 11%, from the northeast 21%, from the south 3%, and from the north 4%. Observations conducted throughout the month recorded 244 instances of calm (windless) conditions, which constituted 8% of the total observations. (Figure 2). Additionally, throughout 2022, the maximum wind speed reached 28-30 m/s. Moreover, the industrial area contains irrigated lands, primarily consisting of household plots, including private gardens and farms. These lands are used for cultivating crops such as *maize*, *millet*, *sudangrass*, *mung beans*, *kidney beans*, *alfalfa*, and other agricultural products. These factors were also taken into account when excavating soil sampling pits. Soil samples were collected from areas around HRES, considering the predominant wind direction as the primary basis for sampling. This industrial area also contains irrigated lands similar to those found in "Navoi Qizilqum Cement" JSC, Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Plant, and Navoi Azot JSC, which are utilized for agricultural purposes. When excavating soil sampling profiles, factors such as the nature of the pollution source, climatic conditions, land use, soil quality, health, and fertility indicators were considered to determine assessment methods and key field sites (Table3).

Table 3

Area	Developed by X.A. Djuvelikyan (2009)	X.A. Djuvelikyan's recommendation (2009), modified by O.N. Imomov (2025)
	Distance from the pollution source, m	
Protected area for pollutants	500–750 m	500 m
Area I	750–1500 m	1200 m
Area II	2 000–8 000 m	3000 m
Area III	8 000–15 000 m	5000 m
Area IV	15000–20 000 m	9300 m
Fon	20 000–50 000 m	20 000 m FON

The contribution of various industrial sectors to soil contamination differs, with emitted compounds varying in chemical composition and form. One of the most common causes of soil contamination is the clustering of multiple industries within the same area, leading to widespread environmental pollution. In Navoi region, industrial zones are surrounded by irrigated soils, which are affected by varying degrees of pollution. Throughout the country, industrial activities

continuously release chemical pollutants into the environment. Once introduced into the soil, these chemicals accumulate within soil layers over time, increasing in concentration and resulting in long-term contamination. Industrial waste, along with gaseous emissions from factories, not only pollutes the atmosphere but also deposits pollutants onto soil surfaces. Wind, precipitation, and wastewater discharge are key factors in spreading contamination, particularly around chemical plants. Pollutants from the sources mentioned above enter the soil in different physical states (liquid, solid, dust, etc.). Scientists worldwide assess the hazardous nature of these pollutants using stress index indicators, which help quantify the level of chemical contamination and its potential risks:

*Various scientists around the world assess the hazardous nature of different chemical substances using stress index indicators
 (S.L. Davidova, V.I. Tagasov, 2002).*

Stress Index of Chemical Substances from a Hazard Perspective		
1.	Carbon monoxide	12
2.	Municipal waste	40
3.	Nitrogen oxides	42
4.	Organic household waste	48
5.	Industrial wastewater	72
6.	Sulfur (II) oxide	72
7.	Untreated sewage water	85
8.	Metallurgical materials	90
9.	Toxic solid waste	120
10.	HRES fuel (smoke emissions)	120
11.	Heavy metals	135

These hazardous stress indicators of various chemical substances impact soil quality, health, and fertility. Wind direction can be unidirectional, bidirectional, or, in some cases, multidirectional (mixed), with varying intensities. Additionally, wind factors and wastewater contribute to pollution. The results above are based on research conducted in the main oasis region of Navoi province's industrial zone. Unlike other regions, in industrial areas, groundwater contamination also plays a significant role. Soil contamination classification for heavy metals is determined based on pollution status, rated as 0, 0.5, or 1 [13]. (Table 4).

Table 4.

Soil pollution indicator scale	
0<0,5 (Low)	If the soil is contaminated by two or fewer heavy metals exceeding the PEC threshold
0.5<1 (Moderate)	If the soil is contaminated by several heavy metals exceeding the RECHU threshold
1< (High)	If the soil is contaminated by many heavy metals exceeding the RECHU threshold

We adopted a conservative approach; therefore, if even a single pollutant exceeds the threshold, soil contamination with heavy metals is classified as "High." This classification is based on the industrial pollution source's affected area, the concentration and duration of chemical pollutants exceeding PEC levels in the soil, and their types [20].

In this context, the pollution levels of the research area's soils, the impact of industrial activities, and the ecological condition were analyzed. Soil contamination varies across the study area. Around the "Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine" JSC, there is no significant visible pollution in the soil cover or water environment, and it is difficult to detect in the upper soil layers. However, around Navoi HRES, pollution in soil cover and water is clearly noticeable. It is also evident in plant cover, and the upper soil layer appears covered with bluish-gray dust. Cement dust and ash residues from combustion are visible in the environment. The study area's atmospheric air composition shows a slight increase in sulfur dioxide and hydrogen fluoride levels. In particular, it is observed that the health, quality, and fertility of soils in Navoi region's industrial centers have been affected by chemical pollutants.

The State of Soil Chemical Pollution. Today, irrigated soil can be polluted from both surface and underground sources. In this case, the dynamics of industrial waste products can move through the soil profile both upward and downward. It can be said that the impact of these pollution factors is correlated with the critical balance of groundwater levels. Depending on this, the impact and pollution levels of underground water vary across different regions. The degree of pollution around industrial enterprises first increases in regions I, II, and III, then decreases in region IV. In the chemical industry (Navoi Azot JSC), pollution levels gradually decrease across regions I, II, III, and IV. In industrial zones, the depth of groundwater plays an important role in the contamination process: Point I: 10-15 meters, Point II: 5-6 meters, Point III: 2-3 meters, Point IV: 1.5-2 meters. Since groundwater levels are shallower at Points III and IV, they participate more actively in the pollution process. In this case, industrial wastewater from chemical plants is mainly concentrated in Point III, leading to localized pollution.

The main causes of contamination include mining, industrial operations, and accidents, which lead to the spread of pollutants in different areas. In Navoi Azot JSC, contamination is highest near wastewater discharge points and gradually decreases with distance. However, for airborne pollutants, the opposite trend is observed. Soil contamination is lower near the chemical plant but increases further away due to the dispersion of industrial emissions by wind. The accumulation of industrial wastewater near irrigated soils leads to groundwater contamination. Additionally, changing wind patterns in the region further contribute to airborne pollution, which then settles on the soil surface. In the vicinity of the Navoi Cement Plant, saline alluvial soils have experienced a significant increase in pollution levels. The contaminants are most concentrated in the 0-30 cm layer of the soil profile. In some industrial areas, pollution is primarily observed in the upper soil layers. The extent and intensity of soil pollution around industrial enterprises vary in both quantity and volume, following dynamic equilibrium principles. Due to the variability of contamination levels, different industrial regions require individualized approaches to soil pollution assessment and management. If industrial zone pollution boundaries are analyzed, all soil samples taken from around the plants and enterprises, including Cement Plant, NMMC, Navoi Azot, HRES, show that the contamination degree in Region I and II is lower compared to Regions III and IV, and the pollution increases from Region I toward Region IV. In industrial enterprises, Region IV (HRES) shows contamination exceeding PEC limits.

The contamination decreases from the upper layers downward. Around the Cement Plant, pollution was lower in Region I and II, but contamination was found in Regions III and IV, showing a pattern similar to the NMMC region. The main sources of industrial soil pollution are industrial dust particles exceeding PEC limits and uncontrolled discharge of industrial wastewater. The pollution condition differs for Navoi Azot JSC and Cement Industry (Cement Plant), where cement construction dust plays a major role. The factors increasing pollution risk include wind and precipitation, which facilitate pollutant accumulation in the soil, as well as the wind factor itself. The highest pollution levels were recorded in Regions III and IV, where contamination was observed in 0-30 cm and 30-50 cm soil layers. Pollution decreased gradually with depth. Due to these pollution sources and influencing factors, soil health, quality, and fertility indicators in industrial zones undergo chemical contamination and transformation. The classification of pollution zones developed by H.A. Djevulkyan was created specifically for chemically polluted industrial enterprises. However, laboratory research has scientifically proven that these pollution distances are not applicable to the irrigated meadow-alluvial soils surrounding HRES.

Figure 1.1.2. Scheme of Soil Cover Pollution Formation in the Territory of Navoi Cement Plant JSC

Based on the obtained results, the pollution distances were modified. Accordingly, the area around HRES should be approximately 1,200 meters, considering the influence of its activities and the flow of the Zarafshan River, which affects the soil sample collection due to the diverse terrain of this area. The Region I distance was also changed to 3,000 meters, influenced by the volume of emissions released into the environment. A similar situation is observed in Region II, where its maximum extent expanded from 500 meters to 5,000 meters. In contrast, the distances in Regions III, IV, and the background region have decreased. Specifically, Region III was reduced from 5,000 meters to 9,300 meters, Region IV shrank from more than 20,000 meters, and the background region decreased from a minimum of 20 km to 500 meters and a maximum of 9,300 meters to 20,000 meters. These findings indicate that chemical contamination of the soil around HRES does not cover as vast areas as chemical industrial enterprises. Instead, pollution reaches its maximum level within Region III around HRES, then gradually declines. The study revealed significant differences in the pollution characteristics around two examined contamination sources. These two sources do not share a common pollution trend, which is linked to factors such as wind direction, the volume, and the form of emissions released into the environment. The new and old HRES stations in Navoi city exhibit different ecological conditions compared to the area around the Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine (NMMC). In this context, the impact of chemical pollutants on the soil was found to be significantly high.

This situation can be explained by the following factors: Firstly, around the HRES facilities, the genetic soil cover has been disturbed and left unmanaged, meaning that no reclamation measures or ecological rehabilitation efforts have been undertaken. Secondly, the spread of smoke emissions generated during the combustion of mazut used in HRES operations

has contributed to environmental pollution. In contrast, the situation around "Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine" JSC differs. Here, the protective zone covers 1,200 meters, with the main pollution occurring in Zones II, III, and IV, indicating that the pollution scale is larger compared to HRES. This is attributed to the higher positioning of the combine's chimney, allowing pollutants to disperse over a wider area, coupled with higher wind speeds in the region. (Figure 1.1.3.)

Figure 1.1.3. Scheme of Soil Cover Pollution Formation Around "NMMC"

The composition of groundwater was studied, and it was determined that heavy metals and other pollutants did not exceed the PEC indicator. From this, it can be concluded that, compared to the chemical contamination of soils around the Cement Plant and NMMC, the physical and chemical properties of soils around Navoi Azot and HRES have undergone changes. The plant ecosystem has also suffered damage over the years. The main factor contributing to the spread of contamination in this area is the wind, along with the significant role of emissions from chemical plants. Around Navoi Azot AJ, pollutants have been found to exceed the PEC indicator in soil layers of 0-5 cm, 5-20 cm, and 20-30 cm within a distance of 500-3000 meters. The negative impact of industrial waste can be observed in irrigated lands used by the local population (Figure 3.1.6).

Figure 1.1.4. The chemical contamination of soils around Navoi Azot AJ and the state of the ecological situation.

The soil indicators, plant life, and water sources around Navoi Azot AJ have also been affected by contamination, which is evident in field conditions. Chemical substances emitted from industrial dust sources can be clearly observed within a 3000-meter radius. In this area, groundwater is located at a depth of 3-5 meters, so it does not significantly contribute to the emergence or spread of contamination. Based on observational and analytical research conducted during the study, it can be concluded that the primary industrial enterprises contributing to chemical contamination of the soil cover in Navoi region are the Navoi Metallurgical Combine (NMMC), Navoi Azot AJ, and the cement plant. Wind is the main factor contributing to the widespread dispersion of chemical contamination. From this perspective, it is crucial to properly allocate agricultural crops around pollution sources, assess soil health, quality, and fertility through indicators, and consider distances from pollution sources when utilizing these lands. (Figure 1.1.5)

Figure 1.1.5. The chemical contamination and ecological condition of soils around Navoi Azot AJ.

The impact of natural or chemical pollutants on soils often alters their upper morphological characteristics, with the extent and duration of these effects varying. The morphological indicators of soils in the study area have also been observed to change. Soil profile excavation for sampling was conducted in accordance with GOST: 17.4.4.02–84, an intergovernmental standard, as well as the recommendations of X.A. Djuvelikyan and the modifications proposed by O. Imomov. GOST: 17.4.4.02–84 is designed to monitor the overall and localized contamination levels of soils affected by industrial, agricultural, household, and transportation pollution sources. It is also used to assess the condition of productive soil layers in low-yield agricultural fields. This standard provides guidelines for soil sample collection, qualitative evaluation of industrial pollutants in soil layers, and contamination level monitoring.

Based on this, soil sampling sites in industrial production areas were selected along wind direction vectors. To monitor the contamination levels of agricultural soils near the Navoi HRES and "Navoi Metallurgical Combine," a sampling site of 10×10 meters was designated per hectare, considering pollution sources, crop type, and terrain. According to this intergovernmental standard, pollutants such as oil, petroleum products, heavy metals, and other contaminants distributed in the surface soil layer were monitored. Soil samples with a point-based characterization were collected in quantities of at least 200 grams from depths of 0–5 cm, 5–30 cm, and 30–50 cm. Soil profile excavation and sample collection were carried out based on the predominant wind direction. In this regard, a 500-meter protective zone around the "Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine" located in Navoi city was considered, and no soil profiles were excavated or samples collected from this area.

Additionally, the vegetation cover and water bodies were also studied. The first soil profile was selected at a distance of 0.9 km from the pollution source, excavated, and soil samples were collected. For research purposes, key study areas were designated based on distances around the industrial zone of Navoi region, specifically around the "Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Combine" JSC at distances of 500 m, 1200 m, 3000 m, 5000 m, 9300 m, and 20,000 m. Similarly, around the HRES (Gas and Steam Power Station) in Navoi city, key study areas were identified at distances of 500 m, 1200 m, 3000 m, 5000 m, 9300 m, and 20,000 m, following the aforementioned modification. In total, 20 key points were identified, soil profiles were excavated, and samples were collected.

Additionally, plant and water samples were collected from these areas. Morphological characteristics of the excavated soil profiles were recorded. The morphological characteristics of the soil profiles and soil samples excavated in the study area are as follows:

SZ-1-10 Profile. Excavated at a point 1200 meters north of the "Qizilqum Cement Production" JSC. The area is dominated by irrigated solonchak-meadow soils, with Sudan grass

cultivated in the vicinity. Mulberry and oleaster (*Elaeagnus*) trees are also present. The soil surface contains numerous small crystallized stones. Cement dust emissions from the pollution source have settled on the soil surface, altering its color and appearance.

0-5 cm. Some plants on the surface are withered, and plant residues are occasionally present. The soil has a medium loamy texture and retains moisture. It has a bluish tint, is weakly compacted, and does not form aggregates. Plant roots, insect burrows, and white mold colonies are visible. Cement dust is evident as a pollutant, transitioning in color and density to the next layer.

5-10 cm. Slightly bluish-gray in color, moderately moist, medium loamy, moderately structured, and moderately compacted. Fewer plant roots, insect burrows, and stones are observed. Pollutants are barely visible. Transitions in color and density to the next layer.

10-16 cm. Light gray, weakly moist, medium loamy, partially structured, and increasing in density with depth. Plant roots are occasionally found, and insect traces are rare. Pollutants are not visible, but stones are abundant. Transitions to the next layer in color.

16-45 cm. Light gray, moisture retained, structureless, non-aggregated, and medium loamy. More compacted compared to the upper layer, with very few plant roots and decomposed residues. No animal traces are observed. Medium and large crystalline particles are present, but no visible pollutants. The next layer transitions with increased moisture and changes in mechanical composition.

45-90 cm. Light gray, high moisture content, heavy loamy texture, non-aggregated, and sandy-structured. Strongly compacted, with no plant roots, animal burrows, or stones. No visible pollutants. Transitions to the next layer with changes in mechanical composition and density.

90-145 cm. Light gray, heavy loamy with a granular texture, high moisture content, and structureless. No visible pollutants, stones, plant roots, or animal burrows.

NK-2-8 Profile. Excavated 3000 meters north of NKMK (Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Plant). The area consists of irrigated meadow-alluvial soils. Wheat is currently cultivated, and sorghum was previously grown. Oleaster trees are present. The impact of pollutants is not visually obvious in the field, but morphological examinations of the soil surface reveal contamination.

0-7 cm. Gray, weakly moist, finely structured, moderately compacted, with a medium loamy texture. Plant roots are abundant. Invertebrate burrows, tracks, and newly formed structures are rare. Transitions to the next layer with changes in moisture.

7-25 cm. Gray, moister than the upper layer, finely structured, moderately compacted, with a medium loamy texture. Plant roots are sparse. Invertebrate burrows, tracks, and newly formed structures are rare. No visible ash residues. Transitions to the next layer in color.

25-66 cm. Gray, highly moist, finely structured, highly compacted, with a heavy loamy mechanical composition. No plant roots observed. No traces of invertebrates, burrows, or newly formed structures. No visible industrial waste residues. Transitions to the next layer with increasing density.

66-105 cm. Gray, highly moist, finely structured, highly compacted, with a heavy loamy mechanical composition. No plant roots observed. No traces of invertebrates, burrows, or newly formed structures. No visible residues of industrial waste. Transitions to the next layer with increasing moisture and density.

105-150 cm. Gray, highly moist, finely structured, moderately compacted, with a heavy loamy granulometric composition. No plant roots observed. No traces of invertebrates, burrows,

or newly formed structures. No visible ash residues. Transitions to the next layer with increasing moisture and density. No visible pollutants in the lower soil layers.

NA-3-12 Profile. Excavated 1200 meters northeast of Navoi Azot JSC. The area consists of irrigated meadow-alluvial soils. Sorghum is currently cultivated, following a previous crop of Sudan grass. Oleaster trees are present in the surroundings. The impact of pollution is visually noticeable in the field, as a thin layer of yellowish industrial dust is observed on the soil surface.

0-10 cm. Gray, moderately dry, moderately structured, moderately compacted, with a medium loamy mechanical composition. Plant roots are abundant. Invertebrate burrows, tracks, and newly formed structures appear occasionally. Industrial pollutants are slightly noticeable compared to the uppermost soil layer, appearing in dust form. Small stones occur sporadically. Moisture changes with depth, transitioning into the next layer.

10-27 cm. Gray, slightly moister than the upper layer, finely structured, moderately compacted, with a heavy loamy mechanical composition. Plant roots are sparse. Invertebrate burrows, tracks, and newly formed structures are rare. No visible industrial waste residues. Transitions to the next layer with changes in color and density.

27-65 cm. Gray, highly moist, finely structured, compacted, with a heavy loamy granulometric composition. No plant roots observed. No traces of invertebrates, burrows, or newly formed structures. Industrial pollution does not visibly affect the soil color. Transitions to the next layer with increasing moisture and density.

65-110 cm. Gray, highly moist, finely structured, moderately compacted, with a heavy loamy granulometric composition. No plant roots observed. No traces of invertebrates, burrows, or newly formed structures. No visible effects of industrial pollution on soil morphology, and no residues detected. Transitions to the next layer with increasing moisture and density.

110-163 cm. Gray, highly moist, finely structured, weakly compacted, with a heavy loamy mechanical composition. No plant roots observed. No traces of invertebrates, burrows, or newly formed structures. No visible residues of industrial waste. Transitions to the next layer with moisture. No pollutants are visible in the lower soil layers. Changes to the next layer based on density.

HRES-4-7 Profile. Excavated 5000 meters north of the HRES area in Navoi city. The area consists of irrigated meadow-alluvial soils. Maize is currently cultivated, following a previous wheat crop. The surroundings contain poplar and willow trees, with juniper trees near the roadside. The impact of pollution is visible in the field, with a thin layer of ash dust on the soil surface.

0-5 cm. Dark gray, moderately moist, finely structured, moderately compacted, with a medium loamy mechanical composition. Plant roots are abundant. Invertebrate burrows, tracks, and newly formed structures are rare. Ash residues appear as fine dust, with small stones present in limited amounts. Moisture changes with depth, transitioning into the next layer.

5-25 cm. Dark gray, with higher moisture content compared to the upper layer, finely structured, moderately compacted, with a medium sandy-loam texture. Plant roots are rarely observed. Few traces of invertebrate burrows and newly formed structures are present. No remnants of ash residues are found. The transition to the next layer occurs gradually in terms of color.

25-58 cm. Gray, highly moist, finely structured, highly compacted, with a heavy sandy-loam texture. No plant roots are observed. No newly formed structures or remnants of industrial waste are present. The transition to the next layer occurs due to its density.

58-112 cm. Gray, highly moist, finely structured, strongly compacted, with a heavy sandy-loam granulometric composition. No plant roots are observed. No traces of invertebrate burrows, tunnels, or newly formed structures are found. No industrial waste residues are present. The transition to the next layer occurs based on moisture content and density.

112-170 cm. Dark gray, highly moist, clayey-structured, compacted, with a heavy sandy-loam granulometric composition. No plant roots are observed. In the lower part of the layer, no traces of invertebrate burrows, tunnels, or newly formed structures are found. No impact of industrial waste is detected. Groundwater emergence was observed, leading to the termination of excavation, as the next layer contains groundwater. No visible pollutants were found in the lower soil layers.

During the excavation of soil profiles, it was observed that the morphological characteristics of the soils in the study area showed significant differences compared to those around the Navoi HRES and Cement Plant. Firstly, near pollution sources, the A, B, and C horizons exhibited uniformity, with groundwater intrusion occurring. Secondly, industrial dust pollutants had accumulated in the upper soil layers.

These findings indicate that industrial pollutants settling on the soil surface have altered key indicators of soil health, quality, and fertility. The same pattern was observed in other excavated profiles, confirming the impact of industrial emissions on soil morphology.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS. The study aims to develop a scientific basis for evaluating soil genetic properties, agricultural technologies for crop production efficiency, crop rotation, meliorative productivity, pollution impact, industrial contamination, soil health, quality, and fertility based on key indicators. As mentioned above, the variety of pollution sources has led to variations in the chemical composition of the soil and their different impacts on it. Currently, in soil science, indicators and criteria for soil chemical contamination have been established. In defining these contamination indicators and criteria, factors such as the area occupied by the pollution source, the quantity, duration, and type of excess chemical substances in the soil compared to PEC standards have been considered. From this perspective, the research assessed the contamination of the study area's soils and the impact of industrial pollution on irrigated soils by evaluating their quality, health, and fertility indicators. The degree of contamination varied across the study area. For instance, in the vicinity of the Navoi Mining and Metallurgical Plant (NMMC), visible contamination on the soil surface or in water environments was minimal. Contamination in the upper soil layers was also not significantly detectable.

However, in the Qizilqum Cement Plant area, the soil cover and water sources showed clear signs of pollution, which were also noticeable in vegetation cover. The upper soil layers exhibited a bluish-gray industrial dust layer. In contrast, around NMMC, visible contamination was minimal, but chemical analyses revealed moderate contamination levels. Similarly, areas near Navoi Azot AJ exhibited contamination levels comparable to those near NMMC. In the Navoi HRES region, soil cover and water sources showed obvious contamination, with visible industrial dust in vegetation cover and a bluish-gray layer of cement dust on the soil surface. The cement plant's dust and waste were visibly present in the surrounding environment. In the study area, atmospheric air samples showed a slight increase in sulfur dioxide and hydrogen fluoride concentrations. The industrial centers of Navoi region have undergone changes in soil health, quality, and fertility due to chemical pollutants. In mining areas, fine limestone dust has accumulated in the soil, affecting biological diversity.

To improve soil properties, bioindication-based reclamation measures have been implemented. The extraction of coal and other minerals has caused ecological and physicochemical damage to the surrounding soil. In Navoi city, the main sources of heavy metal soil contamination include the cement plant, NMMC, Navoi Azot AJ, and hydro-radioelectric power stations. Elevated levels of copper, zinc, lead, and cadmium exceeding PEC standards have been detected in the soil, vegetation, and water bodies around these industrial sites.

CONCLUSION. The deposition of industrial waste into the soil and its contamination process requires an individualized approach. The health, quality, and fertility indicators of soils in industrial zones have been found to be unsatisfactory. The industrial system of enterprises plays a crucial role in the chemical contamination of soils due to industrial waste. Evaluating the contamination levels of chemically polluted soils requires the identification and characterization of appropriate soil indicators based on their physical, chemical, and biological properties. This approach provides a scientific basis for assessing soil health, quality, and fertility using modern methodologies that incorporate soil indicators tailored to industrial pollution conditions.

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